

Automated System to Facilitate Class Attendance using Convolutional Neural Network

Mohammad Barkatullah*, Shad Ahmed* Jannat Un Nayeem Iqra*, Tasnim Amin*, and Md Shakhawat Hossain*

*Dept. of Computer Science and Engineering, Independent University, Bangladesh

Abstract—Tracking attendance is central to educational and institutional management. Traditional attendance recording methods are frequently tricky, time-consuming, and error-prone. To overcome these issues, automatic attendance systems based on biometric artificial intelligence (AI) have been developed as a game-changing solution. In this paper, we suggested a customized convolutional neural network (CNN) model-based student attendance system that leverages facial recognition technology to track student attendance reliably and effectively. Our system is intended to demonstrate that it is feasible to overcome the constraints of standard attendance tracking systems to deliver a more secure and trustworthy alternative. The proposed system was tested and evaluated on a data set of student images, reaching excellent accuracy and indicating its potential for real-world applications. Our findings indicate that the suggested method has the potential to improve attendance tracking in educational and institutional settings considerably. As shown in the classification report and confusion matrix, the CNN model achieved a perfect classification rate with 100% precision, recall, accuracy, and F1-score.

Index Terms—CNN, automatic class attendance, image classification, object detection

I. INTRODUCTION

The traditional daily attendance recording system has always been tiresome, laborious, and prone to make mistakes that rely on manual verification or signature-based procedures [3], [4]. These methods not only take up significant time but also leave themselves open to fraud [12]. To address these challenges, implementing automated attendance systems, particularly biometric artificial intelligence (AI), has emerged as a game-changing response to these issues for the educational and government sectors, where accurate and effective attendance tracking is crucial. In this paper, we have developed a biometric artificial intelligence (AI) based system to track student attendance.

There are many ways to track student attendance, both biometrics and non-biometrics. Most non-biometric systems use punch cards, QR codes, or RFIDs. QR-Code utilizes a barcode, which can be scanned; RFID, on the other hand, uses radio waves, which wave readers can read. These non-biometric methods offer several benefits, such as convenience and precision. However, they also have drawbacks, like needing to complete the attendance process if a student forgets their ID card [12]. Furthermore, RFID systems are prone to fraud as any student can take advantage of their companion's

card, and they can only be used once by one student, thus presenting a time limitation [1].

Biometric attendance systems include fingerprint recognition, palm vein recognition, iris recognition, and face recognition [3]. The main benefit of biometrics is that they link to people's unique physical traits [12]. However, there are drawbacks, too. For instance, fingerprinting is the same as regular attendance marking; students have to wait a while to scan their fingers with a scanner before marking attendance. Iris scanning is the same, but it takes a lot longer.

Facial recognition is a challenging biometric modality due to the wide range of variations that face images experience in the physical world. These variations include illumination, occlusion, facial expression, and head positions [2]. The accuracy of CNN face recognition has been demonstrated to be very high. They can learn robust features from the real-world variations of face images used in training [4]. However, estimating millions of parameters in deep CNNs requires many labeled samples. This restricts the use of CNNs in problems with low training data. In this paper, we used a 2-step approach combining data augmentation and CNN transfer learning for fine-tuning the predefined CNN model. Data augmentation addresses the absence of samples and minimizes overfitting.

The main aim of our study is to find faces and identify them in real time for easy attendance recording. So, the objectives are:

- Real-time student identification via camera and store the person's information.
- Apply transfer learning to optimize model loading.

II. RELATED WORK

One of the most popular biometric identification techniques in computer vision is face recognition. A face-based attendance system usually includes things like getting images, building a set of images, detecting faces, and recognizing faces. In [14], the authors created a Real-Time Multiple Face Recognition System utilizing Deep Learning on an Embedded GPU. The face detection system uses a CNN (convolutional neural network) using face tracking and a deep CNN face detection algorithm. An automated student attendance system was introduced in [10]; the system automatically detects the faces in these images and identifies which students are present to display the attendance information. However, the system did

not support real-time video attendance. According to [11], the proposed method was 'VGG-16', which stands for 'Visualized Generalized Gaussian Gist.' They trained the VGG16 on 3538 student photos, which took around 8 hours to train. Moreover, this method only got 86.3% accuracy, which could be better.

The face recognition method is susceptible to changes in facial expression, posture, and lighting and has considerable limits. [18] came up with an image processing method that combined facial key detection points with gray-scale transformation to make it easier to recognize faces. It makes it easier by adjusting the brightness, contrast, and complexity of the face image features. However, when dealing with low-resolution images, since they have so little feature information and are sensitive to image occlusions, this method leaves out many features and has a shallow recognition rate. Deep learning-based face recognition is more flexible when picking out facial features, and it is good at adapting to changes in lighting and facial expressions. Some popular deep learning-based face recognition techniques include MTCNN, DeepID, FaceNet, and DeepFace. These methods have good self-organization and are adaptable [12]. However, this method has some limitations, which makes it less efficient. [17] proposed to combine CNN and metric learning techniques for face recognition using a multi-inception structure to get facial features. However, it requires a large amount of a data set. In [9], the extracted multilayer features were fused in the subspace to enhance the face recognition effect further; however, due to the large number of parameters, the operation is slow. In [19], the SoftMax layer was replaced by L-SoftMax to prevent overfitting and improve classification results. However, L-SoftMax deepens the network while increasing the running time, which is inefficient. [13] proposed R-CNN, a combination of ResNet and CNN. The problem with this approach is that the network is extensive, and it needs a large amount of data sets.

III. DATASET DESCRIPTION

The dataset utilized in this study consists of 2,000 facial images categorized into four distinct classes. Each class corresponds to a unique individual, and each individual is depicted from five different angles, resulting in 500 images per class. These angles include the right side, left side, downside, upper side, and a straight-on view. Each angle comprises 100 images.

To facilitate model training and evaluation, the data set was meticulously partitioned into training, validation, and testing subsets. The images within each class were shuffled to ensure randomness in data set partitioning. The distribution of data across these subsets is summarized in the following Table. 1:

TABLE I: Dataset Description

Class	No. of images
Mohammad Barkatullah	500
Shad Ahmed	500
Tasnim Amin	500
Iqra	500
Total	2000

The total data set is split into three parts: training data set (70%), validation data set (15%), and test data set (15%). This balanced distribution of images across training, validation, and testing sets ensures that the model is exposed to a diverse range of facial angles and individuals during training while also allowing for robust performance evaluation.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Image Quality Evaluation

Image quality is critical for image classification and object detection using machine learning techniques. Consequently, the success of the image-based automated systems largely relies on the quality images [5]–[8], [15], [16]. The proposed system starts with evaluating the quality of the input images. The quality of the images was evaluated in terms of their sharpness and noise using the reference-less image quality evaluation method proposed by Yagi et al. [16]. Images from focus blur or noise were detected and eliminated for further use in the proposed system.

B. Training the CNN Model

After evaluating the quality of the images, we trained the CNN model using only the good-quality images to identify a student. The model architecture consists of three convolutional layers with ReLU activation, max-pooling, and batch normalization, followed by a flattened layer. Two fully connected layers with dropout = 0.5 are responsible for the final classification into four classes representing individual students.

We conducted training for 30 epochs with an initial learning rate of 0.001. Data augmentation techniques were applied to the training and validation datasets, enhancing the model's ability to recognize students in various facial orientations. The trained CNN model achieved impressive performance, providing a robust foundation for real-time student attendance recognition in the second part of our methodology.

Fig. 1: provides a visual representation of the training process, illustrating how the dataset is divided and used to train the CNN model.

C. Real-time Person Identification using Transfer learning and Information Storage

The second part of our research involved implementing the saved CNN model for real-time person identification. This process was executed using suitable hardware and software infrastructure, allowing the model to analyze video input in real-time. Leveraging its ability to recognize individuals across diverse facial angles, CNN successfully identified persons in various orientations. Subsequently, the identified person's information was systematically recorded and stored in an Excel file for future reference.

Fig. 2: Schematic diagram of student identification system.

V. RESULTS

A. Classification Report

The performance evaluation of our trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model yielded exceptional results. For each of the four classes representing individual students, the classification report showed outstanding precision, recall, accuracy, and F1-score, all reaching 100%. This demonstrates the model's ability to accurately identify students from various facial angles, achieving a perfect classification rate.

TABLE II: Classification Report

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Mohammad Barkatullah	1.00	1.00	1.00	50
Shad Ahmed	1.00	1.00	1.00	50
Tasnim Amin	1.00	1.00	1.00	50
Iqra	1.00	1.00	1.00	50
Accuracy			1.00	200
Macro Avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	200
Weighted Avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	200

B. Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix (Figure 3) further validates the robustness of our CNN model. Each class in the confusion matrix exhibited a balanced distribution, with 25% support for each class, totaling 100%. This balanced distribution reaffirms the model's effectiveness in recognizing individual students and its equal capability to classify students from different angles.

Fig. 3: Confusion matrix of proposed method for identifying four students.

C. Learning Curves

The learning curves provide insights into the model's training process. In the first figure in Figure 4, which illustrates training accuracy versus epochs (Figure 4), we observed a rapid increase in training accuracy from an initial value of approximately 90% to a perfect 100%. Simultaneously, the validation accuracy began at around 40% and gradually converged to 100% over subsequent epochs. In the second figure in Figure 4, depicting training and validation loss versus epochs (Figure 4), the training loss initiated at nearly 0% and gradually approached 0%, indicating that the model effectively learned to minimize its error during training. The validation loss followed a similar pattern, starting at approximately 10%, increasing briefly to around 60%, and eventually converging to 0%, aligning with the model's strong generalization.

The third figure in Figure 4, tracking learning rate versus epochs, demonstrated a consistent decrease in the learning rate from the initial value of 0.001 to 0, indicating that the model's training process successfully converged to optimal values.

These results collectively showcase the exceptional performance and convergence of our CNN model, underscoring its suitability for real-time student attendance recognition and data collection.

Fig. 4: Training and validation curves of the proposed method.

VI. DISCUSSION

In modern life overall, AI-based systems, software, apps, websites, etc., are becoming very easy to use and a necessity as they are becoming a great helping hand for everyone. It has been observed that in each lecture session, almost 5-10 minutes are wasted on taking attendance, and human error cannot be avoided. A customized CNN-based student attendance system will give the respected faculty members some relief from taking manual attendance, and at the same time, it will take attendance accurately. Rfid-based attendance systems cannot be fully trusted as people can swipe other people's cards. However, here, this system will detect a person from a real-time video of a class. Overall, the process is speedy, reliable, robust, and efficient.

The CNN-based model gave an accuracy of 100%. The data set can be made more complex using group photos and even videos, GIFs, etc. Then, it should be tested on how the model performs while detecting particular classes. It was not tested with group photos or videos from where it could detect a particular person or not. After those findings, the model could be made more efficient and complex while detecting a particular person.

Moreover, the system should be able to differentiate between a natural person's face and fake photographs or video graphs of a person. It was tested that now it cannot differentiate between them.

The proposed system can be further worked on for emotion detection. So, while taking attendance of students, it can also suggest to the faculty member throughout a lecture session how well the students are engaged in the class.

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